

How the Ultra-Rich Hack the Tax Code—and Undermine Democracy

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For years, we've been warned about the rise of populism as a threat to democracy. But a far greater danger lurks within the system itself: the ability of wealthy elites to evade the very rules meant to govern them.

The Legal Hackers of the Tax System

One of the clearest examples of this is corporate tax avoidance. Multinational corporations and the ultra-rich employ elite financial and legal experts to exploit loopholes in a complex web of multi-jurisdictional tax laws. The goal? To shift profits and aggressively minimize taxable income.

In his book *A Hacker's Mind: How the Elites Exploit the System*, security analyst and Harvard public policy lecturer Bruce Schneier likens corporate tax lawyers and accountants to hackers. Just as cybercriminals exploit software vulnerabilities for personal gain, these legal and financial engineers manipulate regulatory systems to benefit their wealthy clients.

Columbia Law professor Katharina Pistor, in her book *The Code of Capital: How the Law Creates Wealth and Inequality*, similarly argues that financial laws function like computer code. The tax system isn't software, but it operates in much the same way—processing inputs (financial information) to produce outputs (tax obligations). And just like in software, vulnerabilities exist.

Exploiting the System

The tax code is riddled with complexities: bi-lateral and multi-jurisdictional treaties, obscure accounting rules, and ambiguous legal definitions. This creates endless opportunities for what Schneier calls “legal hackers”—experts who manipulate these gray areas to shift profits offshore, depriving governments of revenue and weakening democracy.

There are two key ways the wealthy exploit the system. First, they lobby legislators to create favorable loopholes—like Donald Trump's tax breaks for oil and gas companies. Second, they game the language and ambiguity of existing tax laws to redefine “compliance” in their favor.

This blurs the lines between public governance and private power, creating a vast asymmetry of knowledge and influence. Those paid to safeguard corporate wealth hold far more power than those tasked with protecting democracy.

The Infamous Double Irish Loophole

To illustrate how the system is gamed, Schneier highlights the now-infamous Double Irish tax avoidance scheme. This loophole allowed corporations to exploit differences in Irish and U.S. tax laws to shift profits offshore.

Here's how it worked:

- U.S. multinationals set up two Irish-registered companies.
- One of these companies was technically tax-resident in a tax haven like Bermuda or the Cayman Islands, where Ireland had no bilateral tax treaty.
- Under Irish law, these were two separate companies. Under U.S. law, they were one entity.

The result? U.S. corporations could funnel profits to the Irish company based in a tax haven, effectively making billions in income disappear from the tax rolls. This strategy was particularly lucrative for tech and pharmaceutical giants, which used the loophole to house intellectual property (IP) and shift profits offshore.

While Ireland outlawed the Double Irish in 2015, corporations were given a five-year grace period to phase it out—ample time for legal hackers to craft the next workaround.

The \$1.4 Trillion Hack

Two key questions remain: How much profit was shifted offshore during the Double Irish's heyday? And where did it all go after the loophole closed?

A recent working paper by economist Navodhya Samarakoon offers some answers. Between 1998 and 2018, U.S. multinationals funneled an estimated \$1.2 to \$1.4 trillion offshore using the Double Irish. To put that in perspective, \$1.4 trillion is five times Ireland's annual gross national income (GNI*).

And that figure might be an underestimate. Samarakoon's research identifies 134 multinationals that likely used the Double Irish, but many more may have remained undetected.

Even after the loophole's closure, only 31-38% of the \$1.4 trillion has been repatriated to the U.S. The rest—62-69%—remains abroad, either in tax havens or in jurisdictions with favorable corporate tax regimes.

Ireland's Role: From Funnel to Sink

Not all of these offshore profits vanished into secrecy. Since the closure of the Double Irish, Ireland has become a major beneficiary of global profit shifting. Corporate tax receipts have surged, suggesting that many multinationals have opted to declare profits in Ireland rather than repatriate them to the U.S.

However, this raises a new question: Will big tech and pharma companies expand their Irish operations to justify these enormous profits? Or will they find new ways to shift income offshore when the next opportunity arises?

The answer lies in the hands of the legal hackers who shape and exploit the tax code. And most of them are paid handsomely to serve the interests of the wealthy.

The Threat to Democracy

Those who manipulate global tax laws wield enormous political power. They enable corporations and the ultra-rich to evade democratic oversight, shifting economic power away from elected governments and into the hands of private wealth.

The Double Irish may be gone, but the game remains the same. Tax avoidance erodes the very foundations of democratic capitalism by concentrating wealth, exacerbating inequality, and fueling public distrust.

For years, politicians have pointed to populism as the greatest threat to democracy. But the real danger isn't coming from the masses—it's coming from the legal and financial elites who quietly rewrite the rules for their own benefit.

What Can Be Done?

To protect democracy, corporate tax reform must be grounded in new democratic principles. Strengthening state capacity to regulate corporate tax practices is essential. This may require curbing the excessive power of intellectual property laws, which have become a key tool in global tax avoidance.

Ultimately, the issue isn't just about taxation—it's about power. In a world where intangible assets and intellectual property dominate, the ability of the ultra-rich to manipulate tax laws will only grow unless governments step up to challenge them.

Democracy cannot survive if the wealthiest players are allowed to operate outside its rules.

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